

**Strengthening organizational Resilience through Industrial Policies:
A systematic analysis**

**Renforcement de la Résilience organisationnelle par les politiques industrielles
: Une analyse systématique**

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ABSTRACT :

This article proposes a systematic literature review to explore how industrial policies strengthen organizational resilience as a performance factor in a changing industrial environment. Industrial policies are seen as playing a crucial role in modernizing firms and enhancing their ability to cope with economic and technological crises. Research conducted in China, Italy, and other emerging economies demonstrates how these policies have fostered innovation, competitiveness, and long-term corporate performance. However, criticisms have arisen regarding excessive centralization and the unequal distribution of resources, which can create imbalances between sectors. This article also highlights the limitations of export-oriented policies and emphasizes the importance of more inclusive institutional reforms to optimize their performance. In summary, organizational resilience is heavily influenced by industrial policies, but their success depends on their flexibility, inclusiveness, and ability to be tailored to the specific needs of companies and industrial sectors. The study suggests that more consideration should be given to balancing state support with organizational flexibility to enhance industrial performance.

Key-words : Industrial policy ; organizational resilience ; performance ; industrial sector ; strengthening

RESUME :

Cet article propose une revue systématique de la littérature pour explorer comment les politiques industrielles renforcent la résilience organisationnelle en tant que facteur de performance dans un environnement industriel en mutation. On considère que les politiques industrielles jouent un rôle crucial dans le soutien de la modernisation des entreprises et de leur capacité à faire face aux crises économiques et technologiques. Les recherches menées en Chine, en Italie et dans d'autres économies émergentes démontrent comment ces politiques ont favorisé l'innovation, la compétitivité et la performance à long terme des entreprises. Cependant, il existe des critiques à l'égard de la centralisation excessive et de l'inégalité dans la répartition des ressources, ce qui peut engendrer des déséquilibres entre les différents secteurs. Dans cet article, il est également mis en évidence les limites des politiques axées sur l'exportation et l'importance de réformes institutionnelles plus inclusives afin d'optimiser leur performance. En résumé, la résilience organisationnelle est grandement influencée par les politiques industrielles, mais leur réussite repose sur leur aptitude à être flexibles, inclusives et adaptées aux besoins particuliers des entreprises et des secteurs industriels. Selon cette étude, il est nécessaire de réfléchir davantage sur l'équilibre entre le soutien étatique et la souplesse organisationnelle afin de renforcer la performance industrielle.

Mots-clés : Politique industrielle ; résilience organisationnelle ; performance ; secteur industriel ; renforcement

1. INTRODUCTION

In a globalized and constantly evolving economic environment, industrial companies face increasingly complex challenges, such as financial crises, technological disruptions, and environmental upheaval. Industrial policies, which are strategic instruments used by governments to stimulate growth and innovation, play a key role in organizational resilience (List, F., 1841), i.e. the ability of companies to adapt and overcome crises. Understanding the interaction between these policies and resilience is crucial not only for public decision-makers but also for business leaders seeking to maintain long-term competitiveness. This topic is particularly relevant in the current context marked by global crises such as the COVID-19 pandemic and geopolitical tensions.

This study aims to explore the extent to which industrial policies contribute to strengthening organizational resilience as a performance factor in the industrial sector. We seek to understand how these policies support innovation, promote firms' adaptability, and strengthen their ability to cope with economic disruption. The central question of this research is, therefore, **How can industrial policies strengthen organizational resilience as a factor of company performance in a changing industrial environment?**

We have chosen the systematic literature review method. This article is structured as follows. First, a conceptualization of the key terms, namely industrial policy and organizational resilience, will be presented to lay the theoretical foundations for the analysis. Next, the methodologies section will outline the techniques for collecting and analyzing the research articles included in the systematic review. The results will then be presented to identify the main lessons emerging from this review, followed by a discussion detailing the impact of industrial policies on corporate resilience. Finally, a general conclusion will summarize the main findings of the study, while opening up avenues for future research.

2. CONCEPTUALIZATION

Before beginning our systematic review, it is preferable first to frame our article by highlighting the key concepts in the context of our bibliographical study. Industrial policy is a set of government measures designed to restructure or strengthen national industry, in particular by promoting innovation and stimulating growth (Shapiro, 2007). Industrial policy enables a rethinking of interventionist approaches to improving national productivity while limiting the risks associated with mismanaging such interventions (Crafts, 2018). It also plays a crucial role in structuring relations between the public and private sectors, providing a better understanding of the role of the state in the economy, particularly in times of crisis (Chick, 2018).

Regarding the notion of resilience, we will define it within industrial context of the 4.0 era. It resides in an organization's ability to anticipate, absorb, and adapt to disruptions while maintaining its essential functions and recovering quickly after a shock (Coutu, 2007). We will consider this concept as a criterion of industrial performance, used to measure how well a company can withstand various internal and external changes in the industrial sector.

3. MATERIAL AND METHODS

To conduct our systematic review of the literature, we followed rigorously structured steps to ensure an exhaustive and objective analysis of the relevant studies.

We chose to adopt a systematic review of the literature, as it is particularly well-suited to addressing our search question. To determine the extent to which industrial policies contribute to strengthening organizational resilience as a performance factor, it is essential to analyze a broad range of multidisciplinary research. Since organizational resilience is a relatively new concept in industrial performance discussions, an exhaustive analysis of existing studies is required to understand its interaction with industrial policies. A systematic review therefore allows us to synthesize and rigorously integrate the body of empirical and theoretical research, to identify the key relationships and underlying mechanisms linking organizational resilience and industrial policies. This approach helps us to avoid bias and offer a documented and provide well-founded response to our problem, considering the diversity of contexts and methodological approaches.

3.1- Collection of articles

We identified two main variables: “industrial policies” and “organizational resilience”. In order to harvest all relevant studies, we performed keyword combinations related to these two variables in the SCOPUS and Web Of Science databases, to ensure a targeted search on these specific themes. **Table 1** shows the combinations made in the search bars of each of SCOPUS and Web Of Science:

Table 1 : Combinations used in our search

Combinations	Query used
1	“Industrial Policy” AND “Governance” AND “Industry”
2	“Corporate Resilience” AND “Industry”
3	“Industrial” AND “Policy” AND “Resilience” AND “Companies”
4	“Industrial Policy” AND “Industrial Resilience” AND “Corporate Resilience” AND “Governance”

Source : Autors

We then applied the PRISMA method to rigorously structure the article selection process. This method enables us to follow a transparent four-step framework (identification, screening, eligibility, and inclusion) to eliminate duplicates, assess the relevance of studies, and retain only those articles meeting the defined criteria. The use of PRISMA thus guarantees the reproducibility of our approach and the credibility of the results obtained. We recorded and classified our articles using two complementary tools: Zotero and Excel. **Figure 1** shows a diagram of how we collected articles using the above-mentioned method.

Figure 1 : PRISMA methodology

Source : Autors

An initial search identified 263 articles from academic databases. After eliminating duplicates, 207 articles were retained for an initial sorting phase. Selection criteria included the relevance of the articles to the issue under study, i.e. the link between industrial policies and organizational resilience, as well as the quality of the articles (based on methodological rigor, data quality and relevance of results). At this stage, 112 articles deemed irrelevant were excluded. Next, 95 articles were further evaluated, and a further 45 were eliminated on the grounds of insufficient quality or limited relevance. Finally, 51 articles were included in the synthesis, providing a solid corpus for analysis.

3.2- Bibliographical analysis of articles

Breakdown of articles by year

We have 51 articles to analyze concerning industrial policies and organizational resilience, spanning the period 2019-2024... We will represent the annual trends of our articles. Figure 2 shows the annual distribution of publications.

Source : Authors

In 2019, articles account for 6.9% of the total. In 2022, the share is 10.3%. In 2023, this share rises to 29.3%, while in 2024, the highest percentage is reached with 41.4% of articles. The years 2020 and 2021 have no publications, representing 0% of the total, so the articles selected are recent.

Distribution of articles by country :

Figure 3 : Distribution of articles by countries

Source : Authors

The graph shows the distribution of the number of articles by country. Certain countries stand out with a higher number of articles published, reflecting a more active contribution to research or publications, while others have a more modest output. This distribution highlights the influence of specific countries in the field studied.

Distribution of articles by methodology :

Figure 4: Distribution of articles by methodology

Source : Authors

This pie chart shows the distribution of articles according to the methodology employed in each study. The majority of articles utilize either quantitative and qualitative approaches, while others adopt comparative or mixed analyses. The 'Mixed' category, highlighted by a distinct red color, reflects studies combining both qualitative and quantitative methods. This visualization offers a clear understanding of the balance between different methodological approaches used in the research.

Distribution of articles by indexed journals :

Figure 5 : Distribution of articles by journal

Source : Autors

This graph illustrates the distribution of articles according to the journals in which they were published. It shows which journals contribute most to the publication of articles in this field of research. This distribution highlights the main sources of scientific dissemination and can guide researchers towards the most influential journals for a better understanding of the academic landscape.

4- RESULTS

We now present the results of our systematic literature review. These results provide an overview of existing studies, highlight key trends and enable us to draw conclusions about the link between industrial policies and organizational resilience.

4.1- Industrial policies

All these authors agree that industrial policies play a decisive role in transforming and strengthening economic sectors, particularly in emerging economies such as China and Italy. Wang, C. et al. (2023) highlight the positive impact of industrial policy on public health and local development in China, notably through the construction of the Third Front. Qiliang, M. et al. (2023) also demonstrate how these policies influence the spatial distribution of industrial land, favoring development in strategic urban areas, while Lin, J. et al. (2024) show that the persistence of government subsidies promotes local economic performance.

The importance of government venture capital in innovation is also highlighted by Ge, G. et al. (2024), who note a positive impact of industrial policies on the number of patents filed. Gomes, A. P. et al. (2023) support this idea, showing that Chinese industrial policy has structured demand for electric vehicles through subsidies and sectoral coordination. This idea is supported by Ding, Y. et al. (2024), who point out that these policies have enhanced China's export potential through government projects. Prodi, E. et al. (2024) take a similar approach in the Italian context, illustrating the resilience of tourism industries to economic shocks, reinforcing the idea that sector-specific industrial policies are needed. Xu, X. et al. (2024) move in the same direction, explaining how the combination of industrial policies and trade liberalization has strengthened exports in China. Liu, X. et al. (2023) add that the government's role in the innovation ecosystem is crucial, particularly in the new-energy vehicle industry, which has helped to sustain innovation on an ongoing basis.

Finally, Bigarelli, D. and Solinas, G. (2024) show that even in a context of industrial contraction, appropriate long-term strategies can enable industrial districts to maintain and grow. These studies all converge on a common finding: the central role of industrial policies in stimulating innovation, structuring strategic industries, and strengthening economic resilience in a variety of contexts, from China to Italy.

However, some authors take issue with these ideas: they agree that, although industrial policies have contributed to economic development, they have significant limitations. García-Herrero and Krystyanczuk (2024) highlight the gap between announced objectives in China and their actual implementation, while Cheang (2024) notes that centralization in Singapore has hampered innovation, especially for SMEs. Thomas (2023) and Bhattacharjea (2022) highlight difficulties in India due to inadequate implementation and regional disparities. Furthermore, Evenett et al (2024) show that subsidies are widely used, but need to be better controlled to avoid inefficiencies. Cherif and Hasanov (2024) argue that export-oriented policies are more effective than import substitution. Wu (2023) and Raushanov and Akhmetov (2023) explain that targeted support is useful, but becomes less effective as industries evolve towards more complex technologies. Finally, Moore et al (2019) show that collective bargaining is essential to reducing economic inequality. These authors criticize overly centralized and protectionist industrial policies. They point to bureaucratic inefficiencies, the failure of import-substitution policies and poor competitiveness of firms due to mismanagement or misaligned incentives. They suggest that export-oriented policies and more inclusive institutional reforms are more effective.

On the other hand, some authors share ideas on the importance of industrial policies in economic development and innovation, but also highlight the challenges and adjustments required. Ekhardt and Breese (2022) show that government policies influence the location decisions of multinationals, while

Lestari et al. (2024) highlight the importance of technology adoption in strengthening the resilience of post-pandemic SMEs. Grilli et al (2022) examine the positive impact of Italy's "Startup Act" on innovative entrepreneurs, while Pineli and Narula (2023) highlight the economic distortions caused by inconsistent policies in Brazil and Mexico. Reynolds (2024) explores the industrial transformation of the United States, with a focus on semiconductors and clean energy. Nahtigal (2024) proposes institutional reforms to support an inclusive knowledge economy, and Vergara (2024) highlights the difficulties developing countries face in implementing effective industrial policies. Giesteira et al (2024) reveal that only certain technological sectors in Brazil benefit from public funding, while Dong et al (2024) show that Chinese companies are adjusting their product ranges to improve their export performance. Finally, Melese and Whitfield (2023) stress the importance of taking family groups into account in industrial policies in Ethiopia. In sum, these authors explore more specific and contextual aspects of industrial policies, such as the role of family groups in developing economies, the importance of industrial clusters for economic resilience, and the impact of the innovation ecosystem on SME growth. They highlight non-traditional aspects such as resilience and cross-sector collaboration to overcome economic challenges.

4.2 – Organisational resilience

Organizational resilience is important for coping with crises and improving business performance, highlighting several key factors. Lopes de Sousa Jabbour et al. (2023), Junaid et al. (2023), and Shahzad et al. (2024) emphasize the integration of technologies such as Industry 4.0 and blockchain to strengthen the resilience of supply chains and organizations. Ranucci and Wang (2024), Garrido-Moreno et al. (2024), and Morales et al. (2019) highlight the central role of innovation and resilient leadership, showing that companies able to adapt quickly survive crises better. In parallel, Badwan (2024) and Barbieri et al. (2024) highlight collaborative strategies, partnerships and diversification to strengthen resilience in the face of economic shocks. Finally, Wichard and Wirtz (2024) show that the ambidexterity of industrial clusters contributes to their resilience. All these authors agree that resilience is crucial to overcoming crises and fostering sustainable business growth.

Furthermore, other authors agree on the central idea that organizational resilience is a key factor in overcoming crises and maintaining performance in different economic and industrial contexts. Gemici, Alpkan, and Giglio (2024) highlight the role of technological management capabilities in strengthening organizational resilience and innovation, while Badwan (2024) shows that supply chain integration and responsiveness increase resilience in the Palestinian manufacturing sector. Micouleau and Robert (2024) emphasize the importance of adaptability in times of crisis, while Ruamchart (2023) highlights agility as a key resilience factor in Thailand's post-pandemic supply chain. Bernard and Loup-Escande (2023) examine how the COVID-19 crisis led to adaptations in ergonomic analyses, demonstrating organizational resilience in the face of major disruption. Bastas and Garza-Reyes (2022) and Hoffmann et al. (2023) explore how manufacturing organizations and industrial clusters have responded to crises, with a particular focus on measures to improve the resilience of local SMEs. Ngo (2022) shows that participatory budgeting practices improve supply chain resilience in Vietnam. Finally, Suryaningtyas et al. (2019) demonstrate that organizational resilience is linked to performance, with a key role played by resilient leadership and organizational culture in ensuring the long-term sustainability of companies. All these authors converge on the idea that resilience, in various forms, is essential for navigating a constantly changing environment.

However, Kennedy and Linnenluecke (2022) explore the link between the circular economy and resilience in their study. They propose a research agenda aimed at analyzing how integrating the circular economy can strengthen organizations' resilience in the face of disruption. The article identifies points of convergence between the two concepts, including the ability to make better use of resources, reduce waste and promote more sustainable production.

5- DISCUSSION

Industrial policies play a key role in building organizational resilience, which in turn is a key factor in industrial performance. To understand this link, we first need to consider that industrial policies create a framework that facilitates companies' proactive response to economic change, crisis or disruption. In particular, they offer support tools that enable companies to innovate, adapt quickly to market dynamics, and maintain their competitiveness :

- **Financial support and subsidies:** The provision of subsidies and other forms of financial support via industrial policies enables companies to better cope with economic uncertainties. By facilitating access to necessary resources, such as funding for research and development or technological upgrading, companies can prepare for possible crises. For example, Chinese companies have been able to improve their export performance and strengthen their resilience thanks to targeted government subsidies, as shown by the work of Wang, C. et al. (2023) and Lin, J. et al. (2024). This ability to equip themselves with tools to anticipate disruptions enables companies to remain competitive even in uncertain economic contexts.
- **Stimulating innovation:** Innovation is one of the key drivers of organizational resilience. Industrial policies, by promoting innovative sectors such as Industry 4.0 technologies or new-energy vehicles, enable companies to strengthen their ability to respond quickly to external challenges. The study by Liu, X. et al. (2023), for example, highlights the importance of government policies in the innovation ecosystem, particularly for the electric vehicle sector in China, where financial and institutional support has enabled continuous growth in innovation, thus improving corporate resilience. Similarly, Italian companies in the tourism sector, as noted by Prodi, E. et al. (2024), have benefited from sector-specific policies that have strengthened their resilience in the face of economic shocks.
- **Adaptability and diversification:** Industrial policies also promote corporate adaptability through incentives to diversify activities. Geographic and sectoral diversification enables companies to limit the risks associated with local or sectoral crises, as demonstrated by Barbieri, E. et al. (2024) in the case of Italian companies that diversified their exports in the face of the COVID-19 shocks. This diversification makes companies more flexible and better prepared to face market uncertainties.
- **Cross-sector collaboration and supply chain integration:** Organizational resilience is also enhanced by industrial policies that encourage cross-sector collaboration and supply chain integration. Badwan (2024) highlights the importance of cross-sector integration and supply chain partnerships in enhancing corporate responsiveness and resilience in the manufacturing sector.

Industrial policies facilitate this collaboration by creating favorable ecosystems where players can share information, innovations and resources, contributing to greater collective resilience.

As part of this analysis, it is relevant to differentiate the impact of industrial policies according to company size, particularly between SMEs and large companies. SMEs, often more agile but with limited resources, can benefit from industrial policies focused on innovation and flexibility, but they sometimes struggle to access subsidies and public support schemes due to their reduced administrative capacity. On the other hand, large companies, although more resilient to crises thanks to their solid financial structures, find it difficult to quickly adjust their strategies to new regulations or rapid economic change. What's more, while large companies benefit more from innovation-oriented policies thanks to their R&D capabilities, SMEs have to rely on partnerships or targeted policies to boost their capacity to innovate and adapt to crises. These differences in impact underline the need to tailor industrial policies to the specific needs of each category of company to maximize their organizational resilience.

However, industrial policies are not without their limitations. One notable criticism is the risk of sectoral favoritism, where certain industries, often technological, receive disproportionate support to the detriment of other, less innovative sectors. García-Herrero and Krystyanczuk (2024) highlight this flaw in Chinese industrial policy, where selected companies receive subsidies without clear transparency, which can create economic imbalances. Similarly, Cheang (2024) criticizes the excessive centralization of industrial policies in Singapore, which has hampered innovation among local SMEs. Another criticism concerns the rigidity of centralized industrial policies, which can lack the flexibility to adapt to specific local needs. Reforms are often necessary to adapt these policies to changing market realities, as noted by Thomas (2023) and Bhattacharjea (2022) in their studies of India.

In conclusion, industrial policies make a significant contribution to organizational resilience by providing companies with the tools they need to innovate, adapt and diversify. These policies help create dynamic industrial ecosystems, where innovation and cross-sector collaboration strengthen companies' ability to overcome crises and maintain long-term performance. However, to maximize their effectiveness, these policies must avoid overly favoring certain sectors to the detriment of others, and continually adapt to the specific needs of local businesses and industries. Organizational resilience, as a performance factor, therefore relies on a balance between effective state support, flexible industrial strategies and constant adaptation to market dynamics.

6- CONCLUSION

The study carried out through this systematic literature review highlights the crucial role of industrial policies in economic development and organizational resilience. Industrial policies, through subsidies, innovation support and sectoral incentives, have been shown to strengthen the ability of companies to adapt to crises, innovate and remain competitive in unstable economic environments. These policies also play a key role in structuring industrial sectors, encouraging the emergence of new markets and the adoption of cutting-edge technologies. In particular, organizational resilience, as a performance lever, is enhanced by synergy between technological innovation, supply chain management and cross-sectoral support. However, the implementation of these policies also presents challenges, not least the risk of resources being concentrated in certain sectors, to the detriment of SMEs or less innovative local industries. A better adaptation of industrial policies to the specific needs of companies and a balanced management of incentives therefore remain essential to maximize their positive impact.

This research raises several questions not addressed in this study. Firstly, it would be interesting to explore in more detail the impact of industrial policies on SMEs in developing countries, where infrastructures and resources are more limited. How can these companies benefit equitably from industrial policies without being marginalized by more technological sectors? Secondly, the link between industrial policies and the ecological transition deserves to be explored further, in particular by examining how these policies can support organizational resilience in the face of the challenges of climate change. Finally, integrating the societal dimension, such as social inclusion and the reduction of inequalities, into organizational resilience strategies could offer an enriching perspective on how industrial policies could promote more inclusive and sustainable development.

ANNEXES

Reference	Year	Country	Journal	Methodology	Theme
Lopes de Sousa Jabbour, A. B., Latan, H., Chiappetta Jabbour, C. J., & Seles, B. M. R. P. (2023). Does applying a circular business model lead to organizational resilience? Mediating effects of industry 4.0 and customers integration. <i>Technological Forecasting & Social Change</i> , 194, 122672.	2023	Brasil	Technological Forecasting & Social Change	Quantitative	Rsl
Junaid, M., Zhang, Q., Cao, M., & Luqman, A. (2023). Nexus between technology-enabled supply chain dynamic capabilities, integration, resilience, and sustainable performance: An empirical examination of healthcare organizations. <i>Technological Forecasting & Social Change</i> , 196, 122828.	2023	Pakistan	Technological Forecasting & Social Change	Quantitative	Rsl
Wang, C., Feng, C., & Bai, C. (2023). Industrial policy and resident health: Historical evidence from China's Third Front construction. <i>Journal of Asian Economics</i> , 89, 101668.	2023	China	Journal of Asian Economics	Quantitative	IP
Ranucci, R., & Wang, S. (2024). Resilience in Top Management Teams: Responding to crisis by focusing on the future. <i>Long Range Planning</i> , 57, 102268.	2024	USA	Long Range Planning	Quantitative	Rsl
Qiliang, M., Linlu, L., & Wenyan, J. (2023). Industrial policy and spatial arrangement of land leasing in China: A case of Jiangsu Province. <i>Cities</i> , 139, 104401.	2023	China	Cities	Quantitative	IP
Lin, J., Wang, X., & Xu, M. (2024). Industrial policy persistence and local economic performance: The role of subsidy allocation in China. <i>Economic Modelling</i> , 141, 106897.	2024	China	Economic Modelling	Quantitative	IP
Garrido-Moreno, A., Martín-Rojas, R., & García-Morales, V. J. (2024). The key role of innovation and organizational resilience in improving business performance: A mixed-methods approach. <i>International Journal of Information Management</i> , 77, 102777.	2024	Spain	International Journal of Information Management	Mixte	Rsl
Ge, G., Xue, J., & Zhang, Q. (2024). Industrial policy and governmental venture capital: Evidence from China. <i>Journal of Corporate Finance</i> , 84, 102532.	2024	China	Journal of Corporate Finance	Quantitative	IP
Pashapour, S., Bozorgi-Amiri, A., Azadeh, A., Ghaderi, S. F., & Keramati, A. (2019). Performance optimization of organizations considering economic resilience factors under uncertainty: A case study of a petrochemical plant. <i>Journal of Cleaner Production</i> , 231, 1526-1541.	2019	Iran	Journal of Cleaner Production	Quantitative	Rsl
Gomes, A. P., Pauls, R., & ten Brink, T. (2023). Industrial policy and the creation of the electric vehicles market in China: Demand structure, sectoral complementarities, and policy coordination. <i>Cambridge Journal of Economics</i> , 47(1), 45-66.	2023	China	Cambridge Journal of Economics	Mixte	IP
Shahzad, K., Helo, P., Ranta, M., & Nousiainen, E. (2024). Blockchain technology for operational excellence and supply chain resilience: A framework based on use cases and an architecture demonstration. <i>Technology Analysis & Strategic Management</i> .	2024	Finland	Technology Analysis & Strategic Management	Mixte	Rsl
Ekhart, G., & Breese, R. (2022). The influence of government upon multinational company manufacturing location decisions. <i>European Management Review</i> , 20(3), 512-529.	2022	United Kingdom	European Management Review	Qualitative	IP

Barbieri, E., Capoani, L., Cattaruzzo, S., & Corò, G. (2024). Export diversification dimensions and performance: Analysis and industrial policy insights from Italian territories over Covid-19 shocks. <i>Socio-Economic Planning Sciences</i> , 94, 101923.	2024	United Kingdom	Socio-Economic Planning Sciences	Quantitative	Rsl
García-Herrero, A., & Krystianczuk, M. (2024). How does China conduct industrial policy: Analyzing words versus deeds. <i>Journal of Industry, Competition and Trade</i> , 24(10), 413-438.	2024	China	Journal of Industry, Competition and Trade	Quantitative	IP
Ding, Y., Zhuang, Y., Zhang, L., & Yang, G. (2024). Industrial policy and potential for export upgrading: Evidence from government-approved projects in China. <i>Economic Modelling</i> , 133, 106668.	2024	China	Economic Modelling	Quantitative	IP
: Lestari, E. D., Hamid, N. A., Shamsuddin, R., Kurniasari, F., & Yaacob, Z. (2024). Investigating the factors of SMEs' business resilience in the post-pandemic crisis of COVID-19 with technology adoption as a quasi-moderator: A multigroup analysis of Indonesian and Malaysian SMEs. <i>Cogent Business & Management</i> .	2024	Indonesia and Malaysia	Cogent Business & Management	Quantitative	IP + Rsl
Wichard, P., & Wirtz, B. W. (2024). Industrial policy and export performance: A case study of Germany's manufacturing sector. <i>Competitiveness Review</i> , 34(3), 519-537.	2024	Germany	Competitiveness Review	Qualitative	Rsl
Morales, S. N., Martínez, L. R., Hernández Gómez, J. A., Romero López, R., & Torres-Argüelles, V. (2019). Predictors of organizational resilience by factorial analysis. <i>International Journal of Engineering Business Management</i> , 11, 1-13.	2019	Mexico	International Journal of Engineering Business Management	Quantitative	Rsl
Cheang, B. (2024). What Can Industrial Policy Do? Evidence from Singapore. <i>The Review of Austrian Economics</i> , 37(1), 1-34.	2024	Singapore	The Review of Austrian Economics	Qualitative	IP
Grilli, L., Mrkajic, B., & Giraudo, E. (2022). Industrial policy, innovative entrepreneurship, and the human capital of founders. <i>Small Business Economics</i> , 60(3), 707-728.	2022	Italy	Small Business Economics	Quantitative	IP
Pineli, A., & Narula, R. (2023). Industrial policy matters: The co-evolution of economic structure, trade, and FDI in Brazil and Mexico, 2000–2015. <i>Journal of Industrial and Business Economics</i> , 50, 399-444.	2023	Brasil	Journal of Industrial and Business Economics	Quantitative	IP
Thomas, J. J. (2023). Employment growth and industrial policy: The challenge for Indian states. <i>The Indian Journal of Labour Economics</i> , 66(1), 113-129.	2023	India	The Indian Journal of Labour Economics	Quantitative	IP
Bhattacharjea, A. (2022). Industrial policy in India since independence. <i>Indian Economic Review</i> , 57, 565-598.	2022	India	Indian Economic Review	Review	IP
Reynolds, E. B. (2024). U.S. industrial transformation and the “how” of 21st century industrial strategy. <i>Journal of Industry, Competition and Trade</i> , 24(8), 1-17.	2024	USA	Journal of Industry, Competition and Trade	Review	IP
Evenett, S., Jakubik, A., Martín, F., & Ruta, M. (2024). The return of industrial policy in data. <i>The World Economy</i> , 47(7), 2762-2788.	2024	USA	The World Economy	Review	IP
Kennedy, S., & Linnenluecke, M. K. (2022). Circular economy and resilience: A research agenda. <i>Business Strategy and The Environment</i> , 31(6), 2754-2765.	2022	Netherlands, Australia	Business Strategy and The Environment	Review	Rsl
Cherif, R., Hasanov, F. The Pitfalls of Protectionism: Import Substitution vs. Export-Oriented Industrial Policy. <i>J Ind Compet Trade</i> 24, 14 (2024). https://doi.org/10.1007/s10842-024-00414-9	2024	India	Journal of Industry, Competition and Trade	Comparative analysis	IP
Nahtigal, M. International economic law and the reinvention of industrial policy: Opportunities, limitations and risks (2024) <i>Human Systems Management</i> , 43 (4), pp. 533-543.	2024	International	Human Systems Management	Review	IP

Prodi, E., Fasone, V., Di Tommaso, M.R. Does industry resilience matter for postshock industrial policy? A focus on tourism-related industries (2024) <i>Tourism Economics</i> , 30 (2), pp. 389-416.	2024	Italy	Tourism Economics	Review	IP
Vergara, S. Industrial and innovation policies in times of crisis: a widening technological divide? (2024) <i>International Journal of Development Issues</i> , .	2024	International	International Journal of Development Issues	Comparative analysis	IP
Giesteira, L.F., Caliani, T., Orsolin-Teixeira, F. Industrial policy in Brazil: empirical evidence in a context of structural changes (2007-2020) [Article@Política industrial no Brasil: evidências empíricas em um contexto de mudanças estruturais (2007-2020)*] (2024) <i>Brazilian Journal of Political Economy</i> , 44 (3), art. no. e243537, .	2024	Brasil	Brazilian Journal of Political Economy	Comparative analysis	IP
Xu, X., Wang, Q., Zhang, M. The complementary effects of 'Made in China 2025' industrial policy and trade liberalisation on China's export of relevant products (2024) <i>Asian Journal of Technology Innovation</i> ,	2024	China	Asian Journal of Technology Innovation	Quantitative	IP
Dong, J., Yu, Z., Shi, X., Yang, Y. Industrial Policy, Product Switching, and Export Performance (2024) <i>China and World Economy</i> , 32 (1), pp. 167-196.	2024	China	China and World Economy	Quantitative	IP
Megyeri, E., Pelle, A., Tabajdi, G. The realities of EU industrial policies analysed through automotive value chain dynamics (2023) <i>Society and Economy</i> , 45 (3), pp. 250-269.	2023	International	Society and Economy	Qualitative	IP
Melese, A.T., Whitfield, L. Industrial policy, local firm growth paths, and capability building in low-income countries: lessons from Ethiopia's floriculture export sector (2023) <i>Industrial and Corporate Change</i> , 32 (4), pp. 956-974.	2023	Ethiopia	Industrial and Corporate Change	Qualitative	IP
Wu, L. Industrial Upgrading, Enterprise Ability Screening and the Transformation of China's Industrial Policy [Article@产业升级、企业甄别难度与中国产业政策转型] (2023) <i>Modern Economic Science</i> , 45 (3), pp. 1-12.	2023	China	Modern Economic Science	Quantitative	IP
Gatto, A., Rusciano, V. INDUSTRIAL POLICY AND FINANCING OF INNOVATION FOR LOCAL DEVELOPMENT: INSIGHTS FROM THE HSINCHU SCIENCE PARK, TAIWAN [Article@PRAMONÉS POLITIKA IR INOVACIJŲ FINANSAVIMAS VIETOS PLĖTRAJ: HSINCHU MOKSLO PARKO TAIIVANE ĮŽVALGOS] (2023) <i>Transformations in Business and Economics</i> , 22 (3), pp. 367-380.	2023	Taiwan	Transformations in Business and Economics	Qualitative	IP
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Bigarelli, D., Solinas, G. Structural Change and Resilience in Industrial Districts. The Case of Carpi [Article@Cambiamento strutturale e resilienza di un distretto industriale. Il caso di Carpi] (2024) <i>Industria</i> , 45 (1), pp. 3-36.	2024	Italy	Industria	Qualitative	IP
Gemici, E., Alpkan, L., Giglio, C. The Role of Technology Management Capabilities in Building Organizational Resilience Capacity and Product Innovativeness: Evidence From the Turkish ICT Industry (2024) <i>IEEE Transactions on Engineering Management</i> , 71, pp. 10846-10861.	2024	Turkey	IEEE Transactions on Engineering Management	Quantitative	Rsl
Badwan, N. Role of supply chain partnership, cross-functional integration, responsiveness and resilience on competitive advantages: empirical evidence from Palestine (2024) <i>TQM Journal</i>	2024	Palestine	TQM Journal	Quantitative	Rsl
Micouleau, D., Robert, B. Organisational factors that favour the development of the unity of effort needed to ensure organisational adaptability (2024) <i>International Journal of Business Continuity and Risk Management</i> , 14 (1), pp. 1-13.	2024	International	International Journal of Business Continuity and Risk Management	Quantitative	Rsl
Ruamchart, B. Supply chain resilience after the Covid-19 pandemic in Thai industry (2023) <i>Uncertain Supply Chain Management</i> , 11 (4), pp. 1617-1626.	2023	Thailand	Uncertain Supply Chain Management	Quantitative	Rsl
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Bastas, A., Garza-Reyes, J.A. Impact of the COVID-19 pandemic on manufacturing operations and supply chain resilience: effects and response strategies (2022) <i>Journal of Manufacturing Technology Management</i> , 33 (5), pp. 962-985.	2022	Northern cyprus	Journal of Manufacturing Technology Management	Qualitative	Rsl
Hoffmann, V.E., Belussi, F., Molina-Morales, F.X., Vieira Pires, D. Clusters under pressure: the impact of a crisis in Italian industrial districts (2023) <i>Entrepreneurship and Regional Development</i> , 35 (3-4), pp. 424-443.	2023	Italy	Entrepreneurship and Regional Development	Quantitative	Rsl
Ngo, Q.-H. The impact of participative budgeting on the supply chain resilience amid COVID-19 pandemic: Empirical evidence from Vietnam (2022) <i>Uncertain Supply Chain Management</i> , 10 (3), pp. 1065-1076.	2022	Vietnam	Uncertain Supply Chain Management	Quantitative	Rsl
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Suryaningtyas, D., Sudiro, A., Eka, A.T., Dodi, W.I. Organizational resilience and organizational performance: Examining the mediating roles of resilient leadership and organizational culture (2019) <i>Academy of Strategic Management Journal</i> , 18 (2), 7 p.	2019	International	Academy of Strategic Management Journal	Quantitative	Rsl

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